

Jazz in the Age of Algorithmic Alienation: AI as a Catalyst for Critical Improvisation

Sri Hanuraga
Faculty of Music
Universitas Pelita Harapan
Tangerang, Banten
sri.hanuraga@uph.edu

Stevie J. Sutanto
Faculty of Music
Universitas Pelita Harapan
Tangerang, Banten
stevie.sutanto@uph.edu

Abstract

This paper investigates how jazz improvisers engage with artificial intelligence (AI) to reorganize and internalize new musical vocabularies. Grounded in Adorno's concept of estrangement and Fumi Okiji's reading of jazz as critique, the project treats improvisation as a method of alienating the familiar to reveal underlying structures. Using manually segmented phrases from constrained improvisations, we extract audio descriptors to train a set of simple autoencoders, projecting each phrase into a latent space. This space is explored through dynamic modulation, visual navigation, and descriptor-based retrieval from a corpus of real recordings. Instead of generating new audio, the system selects and recombines existing materials, preserving expressive detail while encouraging disorientation. These reorganized outputs are internalized and reintroduced into improvisation, generating subconscious 'slippages' that reflect embodied learning. Rather than replacing creativity, the system reframes it, mirroring jazz's historical absorption of external influences. The result is a recursive feedback loop between performer and system, where algorithmic mediation becomes a tool for critique, and improvisation retains its power to estrange, subvert, and expose.

1 Introduction

This work is an inquiry into the processes by which jazz improvisers absorb, reorganize, and internalize new musical vocabularies, specifically through the mediation of artificial intelligence (AI) to generate alienated materials for improvisation. It takes its theoretical foundation from two critical concepts articulated by Adorno and Hullot-Kentor (2006): first, the capacity of musical works to reconfigure the available pool of musical material in a way that reflects and critiques the deteriorating condition of human relations under late capitalism; and second, modern art's ability to mediate empirical reality through technological means, thus rendering the familiar strange (Demers, 2010). The convergence of these ideas finds resonance in Fumi Okiji's reading of jazz as a form of critique (Okiji, 2018), where the improviser's reinterpretation, deviation, deformation, and interruption of written material constitute an act of estrangement that unveils concealed social relations.

2 Jazz Improvisation: Alienation of Written-Out Material

Adorno's notion of alienation is embodied in the practices of jazz improvisers who engage with notated materials not as fixed prescriptions but as starting points for spontaneous reformation. In "Jazz as Critique," Fumi Okiji elaborates that jazz improvisation mediates and estranges the familiar by deforming and reinterpreting the written melody, thus becoming a vehicle of critique. The act of improvisation is, in this view, not merely expressive but deeply critical—a method of revealing the underlying tensions of social life.

This conceptual framework resonates with Gioia (1997) historical account in *The History of Jazz*, where he notes how African Americans, forcibly severed from their native traditions, retained and transformed the cultural elements they could carry—namely music and oral storytelling. Rather than simply adopting European musical structures, they indigenized them through improvisation, forging entirely new genres that have come to define much of modern music. This improvisational transformation reflects a form of cultural resistance and adaptive mastery, a deeply embodied process of absorbing and redefining the musical vocabulary of the colonizer.

3 External Vocabulary

Jazz musicians have historically drawn from external musical sources as a means of expanding their improvisational vocabulary. The list is vast: Art Tatum’s recrafting of jazz piano through European classical music, Charlie Parker’s assimilation of Bach, Herbie Hancock’s experimentation with Messiaen, and John Coltrane’s engagement with Nicholas Slonimsky’s *Thesaurus of Scales and Melodic Patterns*. Brad Mehldau blends Brahms, Wagner, and alternative rock, while Steve Lehman incorporates spectral music and hip-hop. This process of absorption is not mere eclecticism; it involves a rigorous internalization of external material to the point where it becomes part of the improviser’s instinctual toolkit.

This method is well-documented anecdotally. In *Jazz Times*, an article recounts how bassist Gary Peacock observed Herbie Hancock transposing Messiaen’s harmonic vocabulary into jazz standards (Iverson, 2024). The first author’s own educational experience at the Conservatorium van Amsterdam echoes this narrative: students were urged to learn by listening, imitating, playing along with recordings, and only after deep immersion, to abstract and conceptualize the material by analyzing how melodic shapes and target notes connect through scalar movement. This cyclical process of embodiment, abstraction, and re-embodiment is central to jazz pedagogy and the creation of new idioms.

This tradition compels us to diverge from the commonly pursued AI-jazz experimentation—namely, the creation of an interactive music system between humans and AI. Here, AI emerges not merely as a tool, but as a contemporary method for acquiring external vocabulary. If jazz musicians historically turned to European art music, spectralism, or hip-hop to find alien material that could be internalized and transformed, it makes sense in our current technological moment to turn to AI—the most recent major disruptor of human experience. AI-generated material, especially when derived from latent space, provides unfamiliar structures, gestures, and forms that can be alienated and reabsorbed into the improviser’s vocabulary. This is not a rejection of tradition but its logical extension.

4 Reorganization of Musical Materials in the Latent Space

Latent spaces have become increasingly important in creative applications of machine learning, offering new ways to organize, navigate, and manipulate large audio datasets. In recent research, these spaces are often explored for purposes such as style interpolation, descriptor-based synthesis, or generative transformation. For example, Caillon et al. (2020) describe latent space as a domain for sound morphing, real-time synthesis, and intuitive browsing of timbral transformations using dedicated interfaces. Similarly, Yee-King (2022) frames latent spaces as artistic maps—spaces where creators can search, interpolate, and even diverge from training data in exploratory, often improvisational ways. These systems not only generate new variations but also shift the creative process toward a form of active divergence, where the artist navigates between structure and intuition.

Our approach adopts latent space not primarily as a tool for automatic generation, but as a space for listening and reorganization. The process begins with the creation of one or more musical themes, which are then internalized and used as the basis for a constrained improvisation. The recording of this improvisation is manually segmented—guided by auditory intuition and the phrasing sensibilities drawn from the jazz tradition—into smaller units such as motives or gestures.

For example, as seen in Figure 1, we take the first eight notes from a transcription of a speech recording and arrange them into a scale. This was an important first step in adapting bebop gestures to the speech’s pitch material—just as the great pianist Barry Harris says in *The Barry Harris Workshop Video* (Reez, 1998), “Everything comes from scales.”

Figure 1: Speech-derived scale

As Harris demonstrates, bebop lines are constructed by combining passing tones and scales with diatonic seventh chords. As shown in Figures 2 and 3, we adapted these bebop gestures (highlighted in blue, red, and green boxes) to the scale derived from speech. Similarly, numerous other bebop idioms are being incorporated into the speech-derived scale.

Figure 2: Diatonic 7th chords transposed to the speech-derived scale

Figure 3: Speech-derived scale "diatonic 7th chords" combined with passing notes and scales

These segmented materials form the basis for a dataset used to train a simple autoencoder model, which embeds each phrase into a latent space. Rather than relying on predefined theoretical categories (such as pitch class sets or rhythmic cells), we work with audio descriptors, allowing patterns and relationships to emerge from the data itself. Descriptor extraction is done using the FluCoMa library (Tremblay et al., 2021) in Max 9, resulting in a 20-dimensional vector for each phrase that captures harmonic, spectral, dynamic, temporal, and rhythmic characteristics.

Harmonic content is represented by the mean of 12 normalized chroma bins, providing a sense of both tonal center and internal harmonic variation. Dynamic information includes the peak amplitude of each phrase, its standard deviation, and a binary trend indicator that reflects the general loudness direction over time (0 for downward, 1 for upward). Spectral shape is similarly represented through the mean, standard deviation, and binary trend of the spectral centroid, capturing average brightness, variation in timbre, and whether the phrase grows brighter or darker. Temporal and rhythmic features include the duration and an onset density measure—calculated as the number of detected onsets per unit time—scaled and clipped to the [0, 1] range.

The autoencoders are used to learn compressed representations of these descriptors in latent spaces of 4, 2, or 1 dimension(s). These spaces are not designed to generate audio directly; rather, they

serve as an intermediary for navigating and organizing the corpus. When a point in latent space is activated—either through modulation, gesture, or analysis—it is passed through the decoder to reconstruct a descriptor vector. This decoded vector is then used to query a KDTree of the original corpus descriptors, returning the nearest recorded segment. By grounding output in real performance material, we aim to preserve musical details such as phrasing, articulation, and timing that can be lost in abstract or generative representations.

Our decision to work with audio descriptors and corpus-based retrieval, instead of symbolic data or direct audio generation, reflects practical and artistic considerations. Symbolic representations offer clarity and abstraction, but often fail to capture the expressive subtleties central to jazz performance. While neural audio synthesis like RAVE (Caillon and Esling, 2021) offers promising avenues for future work, we chose to begin with a corpus-driven approach to retain the embodied, listening-centered qualities of the source recordings. The latent space, in this context, becomes a map not of sound itself, but of relationships between performance gestures—open to both algorithmic structuring and improvisational play.

Within this framework, we explore and interact with the latent space through a range of simple methods:

- **Latent modulation with dynamic signals:** Each latent dimension is mapped to a slowly evolving signal (e.g., sine waves at varying speeds). These trajectories generate continuously changing decoded descriptors, retrieving shifting yet related material from the corpus and producing layered, evolving textures.
- **Visual navigation in 2D:** The 2D model allows us to move directly across the latent surface using mouse control. Because every point corresponds to a valid decoded descriptor, this approach offers an intuitive and performative mode of interaction.
- **External audio and live input:** Descriptors can also be extracted from live or prerecorded audio and fed into the encoder, allowing the system to respond to external stimuli. In cases where descriptors like onset density are difficult to compute in real time, we substitute manual controls that allow performers to guide the system expressively.

To support improvisational interaction and critical listening, we designed a Max 9 interface that exposes the learned latent space in a performer-friendly way (Figure 4). The system allows users to interact with the 1D, 2D, or 4D latent dimensions using sliders, automated modulation, or direct visual navigation. A looping function freezes the currently active pattern and allows it to be heard repeatedly, helping the performer to focus attention, explore variation, and internalize unfamiliar structures. A corpus playback distribution panel provides real-time feedback on which segments have been played, visualizing the system’s exploration of the corpus. This makes it possible to identify neglected regions, detect repeated fragments, or assess the diversity of material being recalled over time. Together, these tools support a mode of improvisation that is responsive, reflective, and materially grounded.

Figure 4: Interface in Max 9 presentation mode.

Rather than presenting a new technical method, this project offers a creative approach to engaging with familiar tools and processes, exploring how machine learning techniques can support listening,

improvisation, and recontextualization. The system is intentionally simple, and its strength lies in its ability to connect learned representations to the specific nuances of recorded performance material.

5 Internalization of the Reorganized Materials

Once the reorganized materials are explored and retrieved, they are not treated as outputs to be reproduced but as stimuli for learning—fragments to be embodied, revoiced, or unconsciously assimilated by the performer. The internalization process involves several stages. First, novel melodic shapes and intervallic combinations are learned. Next, performers begin mimicking the AI-generated textural gestures, and when the resulting ideas can be learned in their entirety, the performer plays along with them in order to better embody the micro-timing of the ideas. This internalization phase is not just about learning new phrases; it involves physical, aural, and conceptual adjustments. The performer must recalibrate their listening and motor response to accommodate unfamiliar structures that nonetheless carry a trace of the original theme. Over time, repeated practice embeds these ideas into the body of the musician. This leads to what Iyer (2016) calls “patterned responses”—seemingly spontaneous reactions that are actually deeply embedded routines developed over years of improvisation.

This learning process results in “slippages”: subconscious applications of newly internalized material during live improvisation. These slippages, while appearing accidental, are evidence of successful embodiment. They signal that the new material has become part of the musician’s instinctual vocabulary. These spontaneous moments become the source for further alienation, creating a recursive feedback loop between improvisation and AI analysis.

6 Conclusion

Through this method, the improviser becomes both subject and agent of estrangement—simultaneously shaped by and shaping the latent space’s abstract terrain. By encoding musical fragments into this learned topology, where relationships emerge from unsupervised patterns rather than traditional frameworks, the performer encounters their own vocabulary defamiliarized. The process of internalizing these reorganized materials—whether discovered through the latent modulation, visual navigation, or interpolation with external sounds—creates a feedback loop of continuous alienation. What was once familiar (themes, gestures, contours) is perpetually made strange through the latent space’s non-human logic, revealing structural connections and disjunctions that listening alone could not uncover.

This approach diverges from conventional goal-driven machine learning paradigms, instead advocating for a framework that fosters human-machine co-creation and mutual surprise through a dynamic interplay between exploration and expectation. The segmented material, embedded into the latent space, forms a map of the improvisation’s internal relationships—a map navigable through both algorithmic and performative means. Unlike traditional musical analysis, which relies on pre-defined criteria, the model allows similarities to emerge organically from the audio data itself. By working directly with sound rather than symbolic representations (e.g., MIDI), the system preserves the expressive nuances—articulation, dynamics, microtiming—central to jazz’s embodied practice. The live performer, interacting with this space in real time, engages in an improvisational dialogue where their playing triggers latent segments, extending the space beyond static exploration into a dynamic feedback loop.

Rather than imposing rigid uniformity, the inherent complexity of these tools is harnessed as an opportunity to broaden our engagement with generative technologies, embracing their co-creative potential. This use of AI extends rather than rejects jazz’s historical practice of absorbing and subverting external vocabularies. Here, the latent space becomes a new kind of “external” source—one that reorganizes musical ideas according to algorithmic rather than cultural logics. The result is not a technological gimmick but a critical act in the spirit of Adorno and Okiji: the system’s alienating force mirrors late capitalism’s fragmentation of meaning, while the improviser’s embodied resistance (through slippages, reinterpretations, and re-voicings) reasserts jazz as a site of sonic dissent.

Moreover, this mode of collaboration with AI aligns with the conception of paradox as the essence of poetic language (Brooks, 1947). Eschewing linear and deterministic logic, it draws unexpected comparisons—here, between AI and the human improviser—to cultivate richness, ambiguity, and

interpretive depth. The performer's navigation of the latent space encourages a reconciliation of contradictory ideas, adding both aesthetic and intellectual value while uncovering deeper meanings. Ultimately, this work reaffirms improvisation's power to mediate social conditions through sound. By automating estrangement, we expose how creativity operates under algorithmic control—and how, through the performer's bodily engagement with these systems, new modes of critique emerge. The latent space is not just a tool but a collaborator in jazz's enduring project: to make the familiar strange, and in doing so, to hear the fractures of our time.

References

- Adorno, T. W. and Hullo-Kentor, R. (2006). *Philosophy of new music*. University of Minnesota press, Minneapolis London.
- Brooks, C. (1947). The Well Wrought Urn. Studies in the Structure of Poetry. *Modern Language Notes*, 62(6):426.
- Caillon, A., Bitton, A., Gatinet, B., and Esling, P. (2020). Timbre latent space: exploration and creative aspects. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2008.01370*.
- Caillon, A. and Esling, P. (2021). Rave: A variational autoencoder for fast and high-quality neural audio synthesis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.05011*.
- Demers, J. (2010). Material As Sign in Electronica. In *Listening through the noise: the aesthetics of experimental electronic music*, page 43. Oxford university press, Oxford New York.
- Gioia, T. (1997). The Prehistory of Jazz. In *The history of jazz*, page 3. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Iverson, E. (2024). Chronology: How Gary Peacock Sparked the Avant-Garde - JazzTimes.
- Iyer, V. (2016). Improvisation, Action Understanding, and Music Cognition with and without Bodies. In Lewis, G. and Piekut, B., editors, *The Oxford handbook of critical improvisation studies*, Oxford handbooks. Oxford University Press, New York, N.Y. ; Oxford, U.K.
- Okiji, F. (2018). *Jazz as critique: Adorno and black expression revisited*. Stanford University Press, Stanford, California.
- Reez, H. (1998). *The Barry Harris Workshop Video*. Bop City Productions Inc.
- Tremblay, P. A., Roma, G., and Green, O. (2021). Enabling Programmatic Data Mining as Musicking: The Fluid Corpus Manipulation Toolkit. *Computer Music Journal*, 45(2):9–23.
- Yee-King, M. (2022). Latent spaces: A creative approach. In *The language of creative AI: Practices, aesthetics and structures*, pages 137–154. Springer.